

INDIVIDUALISM-COLLECTIVISM AND SOCIAL IDENTITY OF STUDENTS AND ITS IMPACT ON THEIR ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

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Achievement can be defined as a thing done successfully with effort, skill or courage. Individual try to success their life through different means and are driven to succeed for varying reason both internal and external. It is to be investigated Individualism-Collectivism and Social Identity of Students and its Impact on their Academic Achievement. 300 data were collected from public and private university students from Dhaka city following purposive sampling technique. Adjective check list and Individualism-Collectivism scale were used and students' attitude were measured by five-point scale, t test and F test were computed to see the impact of individualism collectivism and social identity on academic achievement. Samples are divided into High Self Oriented (HSO) and High Group Oriented (HGO) and also High Individualism-Collectivism score (Collectivistic) and Low Individualism Collectivism score (Individualistic). Results of the study show that social identity in term of high group oriented and high self-oriented have a significant mean difference ($t=38.46$ $p<.01$). Students with high group oriented have got higher academic achievement and high self-oriented have got low in academic achievement and high individualistic students have highly academic achievement (Mean=3.12) and high collectivistic students have low in academic achievement (Mean=2.94). The results were discussed in the context of individualism-collectivism and social identity perspective in relation to academic achievement phenomena of public and private university students.

Key Words: Individualism-Collectivism, Social Identity, Self-Oriented, Group Oriented, Academic Achievement

The survival of mankind has been contingent on group formation and the establishment of culture. Group formation allows tasks to be divided amongst many individuals instead of just one, and cultures allow individuals to identify how things are and should be done (Triandis, 2012). Harry Triandis (1993) defines culture as “shared attitudes, beliefs, categorizations, expectations, norms, roles, self-definitions, values, and other such elements of subjective culture found among individuals whose interactions were facilitated by shared language, historical period, and geographic region.” Culture helps individuals act in accordance with socially acceptable prototypical practice and values (Triandis, 2012), which decreases uncertainty and increases predictability of behavior (Hogg, 2003). The practices and values associated with a culture aggregate into cultural syndromes (Triandis, 1993). Individualism and collectivism have been discussed in many contexts in the social sciences, such as social systems (Parsons & Shils, 1951), economic development and modernity (Inkeles & Smith, 1974), cultural patterns (Hsu, 1983), values (Hofstede, 1980), and self-concepts (Markus & Kitayama). Since the discussion of individualism and collectivism has been presented in various contexts, it must be noted that research on individualism and collectivism is like “the parable of the blind men, each touching a different side of an elephant” (Triandis, 1993), such that each of these writers touches on different aspects of individualism and collectivism.

Triandis identifies individualism and collectivism as cultural syndromes (Triandis, 1993), whereas Hofstede identifies individualism and collectivism as a cultural dimension (Individualism Collectivism) (Hofstede, 1988). Both social scientists are addressing the same phenomena, but address it differently. According to Triandis (1993), cultural syndromes are established if “the elements of a culture are organized around a central theme, the elements of a culture are more static within the culture than between cultures, and there is co-variation between cultural antecedents and cultures.” Individualism’s central theme is the autonomous individual whereas Collectivism’s central theme is the collective; Individualism and Collectivism are more static within cultures that

exhibit individualistic or collectivistic tendencies; certain cultural antecedents, individual antecedents and levels of optimal distinctiveness vary with either individualistic or collectivistic cultures (Triandis, 1993; Brewer, 1991).

Definition of Individualism-Collectivism

Individualism

The term ‘individualism’ has a great variety of meanings in social and political philosophy. There are at least three types that can be distinguished: (1) ontological individualism, (2) methodological individualism and (3) moral or political individualism. Ontological individualism is the doctrine that social reality consists ultimately, only of persons who choose and act. Collectives, such as a social class, state, or a group, cannot act so they are not considered to have a reality independent of the actions of persons. Methodological individualists hold that the only genuinely scientific propositions in social science are those that can be reduced to the actions, dispositions, and decisions of individuals. According to Triandis (1994) individualism entails giving priority to personal goals over goals of the in-group, whereas collectivism entails giving priority to in-group goals over personal goals. With recent development of Psychology of the Self, important theoretical contributions have been made by several researchers (e.g. Crockett & Luhtanen, 1990; Markus & Kitayama, 1991, Triandis, 1989). Markus and Kitayama (1991) assume that people in different cultures differ in their understanding of themselves, others, and the relationships among people. They propose that degrees of separation or connectedness among individuals vary across cultures. The understanding the individuals are not separate but connected to each other is called the interdependent construal of the self and is supposed to be shared by the Indian subcontinent culture as well as other Asians.

Collectivism

Here "Collectivism treats society as if it were a super-organism existing over and above its individual members which takes the collective in some form (e.g., tribe, race or state to be the primary unit of reality and standard of value" Fred & Miller (1992). And "Collectivism means the subjugation of the individual to a group- whether a race, class or

state does not matter, Collectivism holds that man must be chained to collective action and collective thought for the sake of what is called 'the common good' Ayn Rand (1990). Thus, "Collectivism is a form of anthropomorphism. It attempts to see a group of individuals as having a single identity similar to a person. Collectivism demands that the group be more important than the individual, it requires the Uncertainty Avoidance: "The degree to which the members of a society feel uncomfortable with uncertainty and ambiguity, which leads them to support beliefs promising certainty and to maintain institutions protecting conformity".

Social Identity

Social identity is defined as... a social psychological analysis of the role of self-conception in group membership, group processes, and intergroup relations" (Burke, 2006). The theory is, "explicitly framed by a conviction that collective phenomena cannot be adequately explained in terms of isolated individual processes or interpersonal interaction alone" (Burke, 2006). More simply, it is a theory that provides a core from which psychologists and sociologists can understand the associations and interactions between individuals and the social worlds they inhabit (Liu & Laszlo, 2006). The theory is concerned with the difference between social and personal identity, which underpin the difference between interpersonal and group situations (Brown, 2000). The theory starts with the assumption that social identity is derived primarily from group memberships (Brown, 2000). Group in this instance is a self-conceptualized thought, and, "...exists psychologically if three or more people construe and evaluate themselves in terms of shared attributes that distinguish themselves collectively from other people" (Burke, 2006). Social identity provides a bridge between the individual and the society. It is a relational term which defines people as a function of their similarities and differences with others (Reicher, Spears and Haslam, 2010). Social identity is focused on the structures that differentiate one group from another (Burke and Stets, 1998).

Theories of Social Identity

After the completion of WWII, there was widespread curiosity among social psychologists about the cognitive process's individuals use in

rationalizing irrational behaviors. Henri Tajfel first proposed the concept of social identity in the 1970's after completing a series of "minimal group experiments," which established the basic conditions necessary for individuals to demonstrate in group favoritism and out-group discrimination (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Participants were then instructed to distribute points between in-group and out-group members. Instead of dividing points equally, individuals distributed more points to members of their in-group than to members of the out-group. These findings not only suggest people behave first as group members and secondarily as individuals (Ellemers & Haslam, 2012), but they also began the development of Social Identity Theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Social Identity Theory explains the cognitive process through which individuals develop and conform to social identities. According to Tajfel, social identities are the "part of an individual's self-concept which derives from his knowledge of his membership of a social group (or groups) together with the emotional significance attached to that membership" (Tajfel, 1974). The underlying motivation for individuals to establish a social identity is self enhancement which increases an individual's self-esteem (Tajfel & Turner, 1979; Abrams & Hogg, 2006). Abrams and Hogg (2006) explain that "self-esteem is both a dependent and an independent variable in relation to intergroup behavior: it is a product of specific forms of intergroup behavior, as well as the motivating force for those behaviors."

Academic Achievement

"Achievement encompasses student ability and performance, it is multidimensional. It is intricately related to human growth and cognitive, emotional, social and physical development; it reflects the whole child; it is not related to single instance but occurs across time and levels, through a student life in school and work life." (Steinberger,1993)." Evaluation of educational achievement can be considered as one of the most important aspects of student life. Continuous evaluation of the student's educational achievement during their academic period examining its effective factors is one of the critical and inevitable bases of educational system improvement especially in universities. It plays an important role in developing

better educational plans, prompting educational quality and finally correcting and improving academic managers efficiently (Bakhtiarpor, 2009). Bell (2008) stated that in educational institution, success is measured by academic performance or how well a student meets standards set out by local government and the institution itself. The extent of students in academics may be determined by the grade, a student earns for a period of learning has been done. It is believed that a grade is a primary indicator of such learning. If a learner earns high grades, it is concluded that they may also have learned a lot while low grades indicate lesser learning. However, many experiences and studies found out that there are also several factors that would account for the grade. No single variable can definitely predict grades. (Bagongon & Edpalina, 2009).

Rationale of the study

The present study is to explore the effect individualism-collectivism orientation and social identity on academic achievement. Individualistically oriented group members may display greater accentuation of personal self-esteem and may not share the collective self-esteem of the groups and will show high academic achievement. On the other hand, the collectively oriented subject would show low on academic achievement. It is also expected that person with high group-oriented score will be tended to show high on academic achievement and person with high self-oriented score will be tended to show lower in academic achievement. It was thus, expected that achievement task as a continuum from individualism where persons are considered as distinct units clearly separable from their social context, to collectivism, where people think of themselves not so much as separate entities but rather as members of the groups to which they currently belong. The relevant research question is to specify whether the conditions under which the individualism collectivism, social identity and academic achievement are related or affect each other.

Statement of the problem

After reviewing the literature, the problem of the present study was

1. Is there any difference between academic achievement and individualism-collectivism

2. Is there any difference between academic achievement and social identity in term of high group oriented and high self-oriented students.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the present study was to investigate individualism-collectivism and social identity of the students and its impact of their academic achievement. The specific objectives were to investigate are given as follows:

1. The difference between social identity as high self-oriented and high group oriented and academic achievement.
2. The difference between individualism-collectivism and academic achievement.
3. The difference between socio economic status and academic achievement of the students.

Methods

The present chapter includes methodological details of the present study. In this connection the criteria of the sample, and its selection procedure, design of the study, experimental materials, and the framework of data analysis are discussed here in: -

Participants

The participants of the presents study were comprised of 300 public and private university students. They are purposively selected from six public and private University. Among them 150 are male and 150 are female. The age range of participant is 21to30 years.

Sampling Technique

A purposive sample selection technique would be used for selecting only public and private university students as participants of Dhaka city and a stratified sampling technique would be used in the study. Data collection was completed from different university of Dhaka City. The data for the present study was collected through provides by the researcher. Data would be collected from 3 public university e.g., Dhaka University, Jagannath University, Share Bangla Agricultural University from Dhaka city. Data would also be collected from 03 private university e.g., Eastern University, Southeast University, Daffodil International University from Dhaka city. To get the extreme group of individualism-collectivism score and social identity, both the Scores will arrange separately in order to highest to lowest, thus upper 25% (75) and lower 25% (75) for

both variables will be compared with achievement score.

Measuring Instruments

The following questionnaires were used as measuring instruments: Personal Information Form (PIF), Social Identity Scale, Individualism-Collectivism Scale and Academic Achievement.

Personal Information Form (PIF)

The PIF elicited demographic, personal, and social information about respondent's gender, age, name of institution, educational qualification, family monthly income etc.

Social Identity Scale (SIC)

Social identity scale based on the research of Majeed and Ghosh (1982) & Ghose and Huq (1985), an Adjective Check List (ACL) was developed containing 22 items equally divided into positive and negative items. Adjective checklist was used as stereotypes for self-own group identification. Participant rated each adjective on five-point scale (1= totally true, 5=totally false) for applicability to self / own group. Eleven adjectives are positive and eleven adjectives are negative attributes. To categorized self-oriented and group-oriented group adjective checklist following Majeed and Ghosh (1982) was used. Twenty-two adjectives were used as stereotypes and participant were asked to rate each adjective on a five-point scale ranging from totally true and totally false and own group. Eleven adjectives were positive and eleven are negative attribute (Saha, 2004).

Scoring

All participants rated these adjectives on a five-point scale calculated as Totally True = 5, Partially True= 4, Neither True nor False = 3, Partially False = 2, and Totally False = 1. At the first step, to find out the participants self/group orientation, a difference score ('D' score) was calculated by subtracting of own group rating from own self-rating of each item for each subject separately. Thus, overall, 22 adjectives were summated and a mean 'D' score was calculated for 22 items. Mean 'D' scores were thus obtained separately for all 300 participants. At the second step, the Mean D score of 300 participants were arranged in order to rank from lowest value (-) to highest value (+). Finally lowest 25% (75 Ss) and highest 25% (75 Ss) were selected as high group oriented (HGO) category and

high self-oriented category (HSO) category respectively representing (HGO) and (HSO) of the sample. These extreme group were used as the criterion for social identity.

Individualism-Collectivism Scale (ICS)

To explore the objective of the study the original version of Individualism-collectivism measure developed by Saha & Ghosh (1999) would be used for the present study. Thus, 20 items were selected for the Individualism-Collectivism scale, where 10 items measured individualistic and 10 items measured collectivistic values. Individualistic and collectivistic items were randomly arranged in order to avoid response set. A five-point scale ranging from "Totally Disagree" to "Totally Agree" was used to rate subjects I/C attitudes.

Scoring

Responses of the subject's preferences for each item were taken on a five-point scale ranging from "Totally Disagree" to "Totally Agree". Individualism-Collectivism Scale consisted of 10 collectivistic items and 10 individualistic items. Ten collectivistic statements are rated on a five point scale as 1 for "Totally Disagree" 2 for "Disagree" 3 for "Neither Disagree nor Agree" 4 for "Agree" and 5 for "Totally Agree". A reverse scoring procedure (i.e. Totally Disagree = 5, Disagree = 4, Neither Disagree nor Agree = 3, Agree = 2, and Totally Agree = 1) has been followed for 10 individualistic items. A total score thus calculated for each subject was termed as the I/C score. Hence, a maximum possible score for 10 collectivistic items can be $10 \times 5 = 50$ and a maximum possible score for 10 individualistic items can be $10 \times 1 = 10$. So, a maximum possible I/C score can be $20 \times 5 = 100$. Since the middle point of the 5-point scale is 3, the score of 60 and above would indicate collectivism and below 60 individualisms.

Academic Achievement

Student's academic achievement was measured by collecting CGPA on their last semester. Gradually, at the university level student's academic achievement was measured by applying teacher or instructor made questions at the end of the semester. According to University Grand commission (UGC) grading policy highest CGPA is 4.00.

Design

The study involved a '2 X 2 X 2' factorial

design consisting two levels of Individualism Collectivism (Individualistic Orientation versus Collectivistic Orientation), Social Identity (High Self Oriented versus High Group Oriented) and two levels of University (Public versus private university students) of Dhaka city. The effects of independent variables of individualism collectivism and social identity were observed for academic achievement scores of public and private university students. Therefore, the first task involved is to determine a criterion to be used for categorizing of participants in two groups (i.e., individualistic orientation and collectivistic orientation), and also in terms of social identity (i.e., high self-oriented and high group oriented).

Results

The present chapter reports the results of the study. The obtained data were analyzed by employing Mean, SD, t-test and two-way ANOVA. The results are presented in the following tables. All statistical analyses were carried out using the statistical program SPSS version 16.0 for windows.

Table 1

Mean, SD t-value of Academic Achievement and Social Identity in term of high group oriented and high self-oriented

Social identity	N	Mean	SD	t
HGO	75	3.7508	.17973	38.46
HSO	75	2.3207	.26717	

** (p <0.01)

The scores of social identities were devised in two levels high group oriented (HGO) and high self-oriented (HSO) categorical data, after that, to know the effect of social identity on academic achievement, t-test was utilized. The effect of social identity level was found significant [t=38.46 p<.01]. Respective mean scores suggest that high group-oriented participants have got higher score on academic achievement. To find out the groups in terms of social identity 300 data was ranked in order to lowest to highest as ascending order i.e., lowest score was placed on the top and highest score was in the bottom. Thus, lowest 25% score was treated as High Group Oriented (HGO) and the highest 25% was treated High Self Oriented (HSO). These two groups are

extreme groups.

Table 2

Mean, SD and t-value of academic achievement in term of high and low Individualism Collectivism

Individualism Collectivism	N	Mean	SD	t
High I/C group	75	2.9435	.77940	1.50
Low I/C group	75	3.1280	.71793	

Results shows that mean difference between these two groups are not significant. To find out the groups in terms of Individualism-Collectivism score 300 data was ranked in order to highest to lowest as descending order i.e., highest score was placed on the top and lowest score was in the bottom. Thus, highest 25% score was treated as High I\C group and the lowest 25% was treated as Low I\C group. These two groups are extreme groups

Table 3

Mean, SD and Academic Achievement in term of high and low Family income

Family income	N	Mean	SD	t
High	75	3.3753	.33807	-3.030
Low	75	3.2203	.2866	

*(p <0.05)

Descriptive scores of academic achievements on the level family income of participants shows that the participants of high family income are more success with academic achievement in comparison to participants of low family income. The effect of family income was found significant [t= (-3.030) p <0.05]. Respective mean scores indicate that participants of high family income have got higher score than participants (high and low) of low family income on academic achievement.

Table 4

Mean, SD and t-value of Academic Achievement in term of Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t
Male	150	3.2898	.28662	-2.299
Female	150	3.3781	.37324	

*(p <0.05)

The effect of gender was found significant [t= (199) -2.299; p <0.05] on academic achievement. Respective mean scores show that female participants have got higher academic achievement but only with marginal difference

Table 5

Summary of ANOVA of Academic Achievement by Social Identity and Individualism-Collectivism

Source	SS	df	MS	F	sig
Social identity	75.520	1	75.520	1497.493**	.001
Individualism Collectivism	.099	1	.099	1.955	.164
2-Way interaction SI *IC	.211	1	.211	4.182*	.05
Error	7.363	146	.050		
Total	1466.722	150			

** (p <0.01) * (p <0.05)

Table 5 showed that social identity (F= 75.520, p <.001) had a significant main effect of academic achievement. In other words, the intensity of achieving grade significantly differed depending on whether the respondent were high group oriented or high self-oriented. On the contrary, F-table also indicated that the main effect of academic achievement in accordance with individualism collectivism slightly specific for high individualism-collectivism and low individualism collectivism was not significant. The data also indicated that the interaction between social identity (SI) and individualism-collectivism (F= 4.182, p <0.05) was significant.

Discussion

The general purpose of the present study was to explore Individualism-Collectivism and Social Identity of Students and its Impact on their Academic Achievement. Individualism favor that a human being should think and judge independent respecting nothing more than the sovereignty of a person mind. Generally, an individual is a person or any specific object in a collection. Individually is the processing his or her own need. Collectivism is the principle of giving a group, or family, priority over the single individuals within it. And social identity involves intergroup relation. It may be used to understand various types of group category. On the other hand, Achievement is the need for challenge for personal accomplishment and success in competitive situation. Academic achievement includes the achievement of grade, classroom performance and fear of failure. The individual motives to achieve the goal and those who are individualistic they possess in highly competitive attitudes (Faitar, 2006).

The finding of Table 1 that the Academic

Achievement and Social Identity in term of high group oriented and high self-oriented was highly significant. The mean difference between high group oriented and high self-oriented. The high group oriented have got higher academic achievement. The finding of table 2 that the Academic Achievement and Individualism-Collectivism in term of high and low individualism-collectivism score have a marginal difference. Mean difference High I\C group (individualistic) score and Low I\C group score (collectivistic). Individualistic societies help student to express creativity, ability to move forward (Trumbull, Rothstein-Fisch, & Greenfield, 2000).

From finding of table 3 Academic Achievement and Family income in term of high and low family income. The results showed that there has a significant mean difference between high and low family income participants in academic achievement. The highly family income participants have higher mean score in academic achievement than that of low family income participants. Finding of table 4 showed that there is also difference in academic achievement according to gender. Mean difference score showed that female student has got higher academic achievement than that of male students but only with a marginal difference.

From finding table 5 showed summary of ANOVA by Social identity and individualism collectivism. From F table social identity have a significant main effect on academic achievement. On the contrary, F-table indicated that the main effect of academic achievement in accordance with individualism-collectivism slightly specific for high individualism-collectivism and low

individualism-collectivism was not significant. The data also indicated that the interaction between social identity (SI) and individualism-collectivism was significant.

Conclusion

In the light of above findings, it is concluded that many researchers, educational psychologist, teacher and policy makers are trying to find out the most important determinants related to academic outcome, this study will help them to understand the importance of these factors. So, among others that government should put in place adequate facilities and resources which will make learning encouraging, while the university administrator should try as much as possible to boost the morale of teachers by providing necessary encouragement needed to achieve educational aims.

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